

Evaluation of the carbon footprint of HFC and natural refrigerant transport refrigeration units from a life-cycle perspective

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, the temperature-controlled transport sector has experienced a substantial growth, and this trend is expected to accelerate in the coming years. However, as the sector expands, it becomes imperative to address and mitigate the carbon footprint of transport refrigeration systems. The carbon footprint of a refrigeration system comprises both direct emissions from refrigerant leakage and indirect emissions derived from energy consumption.

In this study, dynamic numerical simulations are used to evaluate the annual performance of a conventional HFC (R134a) transport refrigeration unit and of a newly developed natural refrigerant (R744) one employed in a multi-drop delivery mission in urban environment. Additionally, a simplified life cycle approach is used to compare the carbon footprint of these cooling units across various stages of the system supply chain, including refrigerant production and recycling, unit manufacturing, operation and disposal.

Results show that the R744 unit presents significantly higher COP for high ambient temperatures, while its performance is degraded for low ambient temperatures due to low duty cycle. On annual basis, the R744 unit COP is 27.5% higher than the R134a one. However, the increased weight of the R744 unit results in significantly higher emissions associated with fuel consumption required to transport the unit weight, leading to slightly higher fuel related emissions (+6.4%) for the R744 unit.

Nevertheless, the high GWP of R134a contributes to substantial direct emissions due to refrigerant leakages, resulting in an overall 34.6% reduction in the lifetime CO₂ equivalent emissions for the R744 unit when considering the total emissions.

Keywords: Refrigerated transport, Life-Cycle Assessment, Carbon footprint, Carbon Dioxide, HFC.

1. INTRODUCTION

Temperature is the main factor affecting the safety and quality of perishable products, such as food and pharmaceuticals (Hertog et al., 2014). The cooling steps which guarantee the need to maintain perishable products in a specific temperature range throughout their entire supply chain are commonly named “cold chain”. The cold chain comprehends the whole process of production stage, initial pre-cooling, storage and transport of products, their distribution and final domestic refrigeration by the end-user (Mercier et al., 2017).

According to a recent IIR informatory note (2021), approximately 40% of the total food production for human consumption should be refrigerated at a certain point in their life. However, a good and efficient cold chain

for perishable products is not always guaranteed, and this results in food losses due to a lack of refrigeration equal to approximately 12% of the total food production for human consumption (IIR, 2021). A more extensive and effective cold chain could significantly reduce food losses and consequently improve global food safety and security.

Within the cold chain, transport operations are a key link to ensure preservation of perishable goods at adequate temperature level. The road transport refrigeration and last-mile delivery sector experienced a significant growth in the last few years. Yang et al. (2021) report that the COVID-19 outbreak has strongly accelerated online grocery shopping in UK and that weekly home delivery orders have registered a 38% increase compared to the pre-pandemic period. Fertel et al. (2023) report that the number of vehicles in France with a registered ATP certificate (Agreement on the international carriage of perishable foodstuffs and on the special equipment to be used for such carriage - United Nations, 2020) has increased by approximately 13% from 2017 to 2021.

In the next future, the road refrigerated transport sector is expected to rise at an even greater rate (Yang et al., 2021; Maiorino et al., 2021; Oko-Recherche et al., 2021), highlighting the crucial importance of an accurate assessment of the temperature-controlled transport carbon footprint, to evaluate and mitigate both the direct (linked to greenhouse gases emissions) and indirect (linked to energy consumption) emissions related to transport cooling units life cycle in its entirety.

IIR (2021) reported that the global refrigerated fleet in 2021 consisted in 3.4 millions of vehicles and, according to the assumptions of that study, the related global emissions were about 50 Mt_{CO₂,eq}, representing nearly 25% of the total cold chain emissions. Moreover, a recent research study by Minetto et al. (2023a) reported that the European road refrigerated fleet consumes more than 3500 GWh of primary energy on annual basis and that an improved fleet (with improved insulation, natural refrigerant units, electrification and improved controls) could potentially lead to more than 28% reduction in primary energy consumption and more than 66% reduction in equivalent CO₂ emissions.

However, despite the significant environmental impact highlighted by the above-mentioned researches, only a few studies related to the life-cycle environmental impact of food transport refrigeration systems are available in literature.

Wu et al. (2013) presented a model to assess the carbon footprint of food transport refrigeration systems employing different refrigerants (R404A, R410A and R744) during their production, transport, use, repair and recycling phases. Mainly due to its high Global Warming Potential (GWP), the total carbon footprint of food transport refrigeration systems equipped with R404A was found out to be larger than with the other refrigerants. Despite being characterized by the lowest GWP, R744 equipped systems may lead to a higher carbon footprint compared with an R410A system in high environmental temperature operation due to a reduction in the cooling unit efficiency. Results show that 65-86% of the emissions of the system life cycle come from the energy consumption needed to power the cooling unit and to carry the additional weight of the refrigeration system on the vehicle.

Li (2017) developed a numerical model based on the assessment of evaluation indexes to investigate the greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions of a R452A and of a traditional R404A food transport refrigeration systems during their entire life cycle. Results show that the use of R452A can lead to a total emission

reduction (direct and indirect) between 5% and 15% over the system life cycle. In addition, the author highlighted that the operating conditions highly influence emissions: a reduction of the external temperature from 32°C to 15.5°C could reduce up to 60% the emissions of fresh product transport, while an increase of the evaporating temperature set-point from -23°C to 10°C can lead to more than 80% emission reduction, compatibly with the temperature set-point necessary for the specific transported products.

Wu et al. (2022a) compared the carbon footprint of a conventional vapor-compression refrigeration system with an alternative phase change material (PCM)-based cold storage system in refrigerated truck applications, considering also the influence of the refrigerant choice (R404A, R410A and R744). The use of the PCM-based system leads to a reduction between 22% and 56% of the total carbon footprint compared to the conventional vapor-compression system. Results show that most of the CO₂ equivalent emissions are related to the operation of the cooling system (84%-91% of the total for the vapor-compression system, 68% for the PCM-based system). Regarding the vapor-compression system, the use of R410A and R744 leads to a reduction of the carbon footprint over a lifetime of 10 years equal to 1.5%-1.8% and 3.2%-3.9%, respectively. Another research study from the same research group (Wu et al., 2022b) highlights that the annual carbon footprint of the refrigerated vehicles fleet in China could increase by approximately 2.5 times from 2019 to 2025 without intervention towards technological improvement, such as cleaner primary energy sources (electrification and hydrogen fuel cell technology).

As emerged from scientific literature review, the choice of the refrigerant can have a significant impact on the total life-cycle carbon footprint of a road transport refrigeration system, mainly due to the difference in GWP between traditionally used HFC or HFO refrigerants and natural refrigerants. The effect on temperature-controlled transport sustainability is significant, as synthetic refrigerants are still used in almost the entirety of the sector. As an example, Cavalier et al. (2023) reported that 81% of the total refrigerant mass employed in temperature-controlled transport in France in 2022 is still R404A (characterized by a GWP equal to 3260 kg_{CO₂,eq}/kg_{refrigerant}), despite almost the entirety of new equipment is based on the use of R452A (GWP = 2140 kg_{CO₂,eq}/kg_{refrigerant}). On the other hand, natural refrigerants are characterized by almost negligible GWP (1 kg_{CO₂,eq}/kg_{refrigerant} for R744) and the interest towards their use in transport refrigeration applications is growing, also due to the progressive limitation and phase-out of HFC/HFO refrigerants that will occur in the next few years following the EU F-Gas Regulation (European Commission, 2014). A complete review on proposed solutions based on the employment of natural refrigerants in transport refrigeration can be found in Minetto et al. (2023b).

The objective of the present study is therefore the evaluation of the carbon footprint of a traditional HFC-based (R134a) road transport refrigeration unit and of a newly developed natural refrigerant (R744) unit, from a life-cycle perspective.

Since literature results highlighted that the vast majority of the total lifetime carbon footprint of road transport refrigeration systems lies in the use phase, accounting for approximately 96% of a refrigerated truck's total GHG emissions (Wu et al., 2022b), in this study a dynamic numerical modelling approach has been used for the accurate evaluation, on a monthly basis, of the performance and of the actual energy demand of a R134a and a R744 transport refrigeration units employed in urban multi-drop delivery missions, thus avoiding a parametrical evaluation, based on assumed indexes, of the energy consumption of the cooling units during operation.

As a subsequent step, to evaluate and compare the environmental sustainability of road transport cooling systems employing traditional HFC refrigerants (R134a) or natural refrigerants (R744), the overall environmental impact of the life cycle of the two units has been assessed, integrating the carbon footprint linked to the operation of the cooling units (evaluated in detail from the cooling units dynamic model results) with the carbon footprint linked to the refrigerants production and disposal, to the refrigerants leakage in the atmosphere and to the cooling units manufacturing and dismissal (calculated through parametrical evaluation based on literature studies).

2. THE COOLING UNITS

This study focuses on the evaluation of the environmental impact of two different cooling units, one employing a synthetic refrigerant, the other employing a natural refrigerant, both designed to provide Medium-Temperature (MT) refrigeration for the preservation of fresh or perishable goods during road transport applications. The considered application is the temperature control inside the insulated box mounted on a Light Commercial Vehicle (LCV). The design cooling power of the R134a units was sized according to technical practice for a small LCV application resulting in approximately 3 kW of cooling power with $T_{amb} = 30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_i = 0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The R744 unit size, due to the scarcity of small-scale components (mainly compressor and ejector) resulted to have 6 kW cooling power in the same conditions. This will affect the R744 unit performance and will be discussed in detail in the results section.

A simple R134a vapor compression unit (Figure 1a) is considered in this study, as representative of the current road transport refrigeration sector (Tassou et al., 2009; Cavalier and Tassou, 2011; Michienau et al., 2014). Figure 1b reports the pressure-specific enthalpy (p-h) diagram of the R134a refrigerant during steady-state operation with $T_{amb} = 30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_i = 0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\omega_{comp} = 1450\text{ rev min}^{-1}$, with reference to Figure 1a schematic.

Figure 1 – R134a cooling unit: (a) operational schematic; (b) p-h diagram of the system operating points with $T_{amb} = 30^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_i = 0^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\omega_{comp} = 1450 \text{ rev min}^{-1}$.

As an alternative of the R134a cooling unit described above, a newly developed cooling unit, which has been previously presented and described in Artuso et al. (2020) and Fabris et al. (2021) and characterized by the use of a natural fluid (R744) as the refrigerant, is considered in this study. The R744 cooling unit schematic is presented in Figure 2a. Figure 2b reports the pressure-specific enthalpy (p-h) diagram of the R744 refrigerant during steady-state operation with $T_{amb} = 30^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_i = 0^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\omega_{comp} = 1450 \text{ rev min}^{-1}$.

Figure 2 – R744 cooling unit: (a) operational schematic; (b) p-h diagram of the system operating points with $T_{amb} = 30^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_i = 0^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\omega_{comp} = 1450 \text{ rev min}^{-1}$.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Refrigeration systems numerical model

A dynamic numerical model of both the cooling units is developed using the commercial multi-physics software Simcenter Amesim 2021. The numerical approach of the software is based on the discretization of real components in lumped parameters elements, connected to describe the entire system. Each element is described by nonlinear time-dependent differential equations involving the state variables. Equations are then assembled in a system of differential equations, according to the elements connection.

The compressors are modelled using a fixed displacement compressor model. From the compressors operating data available in the commercial data sheets, the different volumetric efficiency η_{vol} and the overall compression efficiency η_{comp} are interpolated as functions of the pressure ratio r_p and the rotational speed ω_{comp} . The finned-coil heat exchangers are approximated to simple straight tube in tube counter-flow configurations. The counter-flow design is then discretized into N longitudinal lumped volumes (N=6 for the R134a heat exchangers, N=10 for the R744 evaporators, N=12 for the R744 gas cooler/condenser). Internal convection between the refrigerant and the internal wall, conduction through wall and fins and external convection between the fins and the outside air are considered for each of the lumped volumes in which the heat exchangers are discretized. The heat transfer coefficients are evaluated through empirical correlations, available in the literature. For the refrigerant, mass and energy balances are evaluated in each discretized element. The R744 ejector performance is modelled using the interpolating functions reported by Banasiak et al. (2015), based on the results of an experimental evaluation of the performance of a high-pressure lift multi-ejector pack designed for R744 refrigerating systems, which describe the ejector operation as a function of the boundary conditions (motive nozzle, suction nozzle and discharge port conditions).

A vehicle insulated body with an internal volume of 11.89 m^3 is considered, for both the R134a and the R744 unit numerical models. A global heat transfer coefficient equal to $K = 0.36 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$ was experimentally

evaluated in a previous work (Artuso et al., 2019). The refrigerated box thermal characterization is modelled using a network of lumped thermal capacities and resistances. The dynamic internal air volume transient heat balance considers the cooling power provided by the refrigeration unit, convection with the internal wall temperature and with the transported goods, infiltrations of ambient air into the insulated body during the opening of the vehicle's doors, conductive heat through the box wall and radiation exchanges insisting on the average external surface temperature.

A detailed description of the components dimensions and geometries, as well as of the dynamic numerical modelling approach, including the formulation of the used differential equations used to describe the dynamic behaviour of the refrigeration systems and of the empirical correlations used to define the heat transfer coefficients, can be found in Artuso et al. (2019), Artuso et al. (2020), Fabris et al. (2021) and Fabris et al. (2022).

3.2 Refrigeration systems operation

The performance of the R134a and R744 cooling units are evaluated during operation in a fixed-structure short-range multi-drop delivery mission of temperature-controlled goods in an urban environment. The mission simulates a typical daily local distribution activity, characterized by seven doors openings for product delivery in the morning and seven in the afternoon. The mission profile is defined setting the vehicle speed, the doors openings and the amount of perishable goods discharged at each delivery point, as a function of time. The vehicle speed is based on the Worldwide Harmonized Light Vehicles Test Cycle WLTC (United Nations, 2021) low and medium phases repeated and combined to be representative of an urban delivery mission scenario (Fabris et al., 2022).

The compressors of both the cooling units are assumed to operate at fixed speed, equal to the rated speed $\omega_{comp} = 1450 \text{ rev min}^{-1}$. The compressors ON/OFF control is set by a thermostat with a 4°C hysteresis, to maintain the air temperature T_i inside the refrigerated cargo space between -1°C and 3°C along the whole delivery mission. The energy required to run the compressor is assumed to be taken from the vehicle internal combustion engine by means of a belt (with constant efficiency equal to 0.75), converted by an electrical generator (conversion efficiency assumed equal to 0.85) and then fed to the unit compressor.

To compare the performance of the R134a and the R744 cooling on a yearly basis, a mean day for every month in the year is considered for the numerical simulations, leading to a total of 12 daily simulations for each system. The climate of Athens is adopted, as representative of hot European climate. The environmental temperature, relative humidity and solar radiation intensity, available in the Energy Plus online database (Energy Plus, 2022), were collected for all the days of each month of the year, averaged hourly to obtain the climatic profile of the mean day of each of the months and used as an input of the numerical models.

3.3 Life cycle evaluation

In this study, the average age of LCVs in use in Europe, equal to 12.0 years (ACEA, 2023), is assumed as the cooling units' lifetime. The yearly operation is assumed to be characterized by repetitions of the same short-range delivery mission, 5 days/week for 50 weeks (Li, 2017), equally distributed in the 12 months. Within the above-mentioned lifetime, the total carbon footprint of refrigeration units is evaluated taking into account both the direct and indirect emissions, including the main emissions sources during both the operation period

(energy conversion emissions and refrigerant leakage) and the commissioning and decommissioning of the unit (refrigerant production and recycling and components construction).

3.3.1 Operational leakage emissions

The greenhouse gas effect of a gas is measured through the Global Warming Potential, usually referred to the reference time frame of 100 years (GWP_{100}) and to CO_2 (GWP_{100} for R744 = 1 $kg_{CO_2,eq}/kg_{R134a}$). The GWP_{100} of R134a refrigerant is defined to be equal to 1526 $kg_{CO_2,eq}/kg_{R134a}$ by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2021). The refrigerant charge of the R134a cooling unit, representative of current market small trucks and vans applications, is assumed to be equal to 2.0 kg (Tassou et al., 2009). Previous studies in literature also report that, considering a fixed cooling power production with a R744 system instead of the traditional HFC system, the R744 charge would be 1.3-2.3 times the refrigerant charge of the HFC system (Karampour and Sawalha, 2018; Aprea et al., 2012; Rossi et al., 2021). In this study a R744-HFC charge ratio equal to 2.3 kg_{R744}/kg_{HFC} is conservatively assumed. An annual leakage rate of the refrigerant during operation, compared to the total refrigerant charge, equal to 10-37% (Tassou et al., 2009), 10-25% (Li, 2017), 5-25% (Wu et al., 2022b), as well as 165% of the initial charge over a 10 years lifetime (United Nations, 2017), is reported in literature. As a representative value for the above-mentioned figures, an average annual leakage rate equal to the 15% of the total refrigerant charge is assumed in this study. Moreover, a 0.1% annual refrigerant leakage during maintenance operations is considered (Wu et al., 2013).

3.3.2 Fuel consumption emissions

The refrigeration unit is responsible for a portion of the emissions caused by the vehicle internal combustion engine. This share is obtained accounting the energy consumed by the refrigeration unit itself and the fuel consumption needed to transport the mass of the refrigeration unit along with the vehicle.

To quantify these emissions, the two different emission factors have been assessed using a dynamic numerical model of the refrigerated vehicle which include the engine emissions maps, the driveline and a simplified vehicle dynamics (Fabris et al., 2022). In the model, the engine response and the emissions of a four cylinders Euro4 turbodiesel 1.9 l internal combustion engine were modelled through interpolation of the corresponding experimental bench test measurements on the considered engine (torque, fuel consumption, pollutant emissions) reported in De Simio et al. (2010). A carbon emission factor equal to 2.578 $kg_{CO_2,eq}/L_{diesel}$ (Lawton et al., 2019) was considered for the evaluation of the equivalent CO_2 emissions of diesel fuel.

Firstly, the reference emissions of the considered engine have been characterized using a full WLTC cycle, considering the LCV mass (2000 kg) and 1000 kg of transported goods. Simulation results are in good agreement with literature review. The goods mass conversion factor resulted to be 375 $g_{CO_2,eq}/(t\cdot km)$, which is reasonable compared to the value reported by ICCT, 2021, equal to 307 $g_{CO_2,eq}/(t\cdot km)$. The engine conversion factor, referred only to the driving loads, is equal to 735 $g_{CO_2,eq}/kWh$, with an average thermal engine efficiency of 34%, which is reasonable for the considered application.

After that, a sensitivity study of the CO_2 equivalent emissions over the driving cycle has been conducted by changing the mass of the vehicle and by adding a constant power load to the engine shaft, in separate simulations. Results are reported in Figure 3.

According to the simulations, the average emission conversion factor for the unit additional energy load on the engine resulted in $405.6 \text{ g}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{eq}}/\text{kWh}$, while the conversion factor for the unit additional mass on the vehicle was quantified in $37.5 \text{ g}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{eq}}/(\text{t}\cdot\text{km})$.

Figure 3 – Equivalent carbon emissions factor in a WLTC mission for LCV: (a) per unit of energy requested in addition to the driving loads; (b) per unit of weight (and distance) added to the vehicle frame.

The results of the 12 daily missions simulations described in Section 3.2 are used to define the actual additional energy requested to the internal combustion engine to run the cooling unit on a yearly basis, while the cooling unit mass is assessed by summing the weight of the unit main components, as it will be discussed in Section 4.2.

3.3.3 Unit production and end of life

An overall carbon footprint of the R134a production process equal to $6.6 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{eq}}/\text{kg}_{\text{R134a}}$ is considered (McCulloch and Lindley, 2003). Conversely, R744 is mostly recovered from industrial processes through Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS). An average carbon footprint of the CCS process, based on different technologies, is estimated equal to $0.14 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{eq}}/\text{kg}_{\text{CO}_2}$ (Rubin et al., 2015). In addition to CCS, a CO_2 compression and purification process is necessary to obtain a purity content of at least 95% and a limited amount of H_2O and non-condensable gases content, resulting in an additional carbon footprint linked to these processes equal to $0.04 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{eq}}/\text{kg}_{\text{CO}_2}$ (Posch and Haider, 2012). A 2% of the system refrigerant charge is assumed to leak during the assembly process (Wu et al., 2013).

Regarding the refrigerants disposal at the cooling units end of life, it is assumed that only 70% of the R134a refrigerant charge can be recovered and regenerated by filtering and distillation (Cascini et al., 2016). The energy requirement for refrigerant recycling is assumed equal to $4.34 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{eq}}/\text{kg}$ (Wu et al., 2022b). The non-recoverable R134a charge is assumed to be released in the atmosphere, as well as the entirety of the R744 unit charge.

Components available in the market and suitable for the specific application are selected to estimate the weight of the cooling units (see Section 4.2). Electrical energy consumption factors equal to 4.22 kWh/kg and

to 2.69 kWh/kg are assumed for the cooling units manufacturing and recycling processes, respectively (Wu et al., 2022b). The carbon footprint linked to these processes is evaluated considering the average GHG emission intensity of the electricity generation in Europe, equal to 275 g_{CO₂,eq}/kWh (EEA, 2022).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Cooling units annual performance

Being emissions during service the largest GHG emitter in transport vehicles (Wu et al., 2013; Li, 2017; Wu et al., 2022a), the performance of the R134a unit and of the R744 unit are firstly evaluated in detail through dynamic numerical simulations of a short-range multi-drop delivery mission in urban environment, thus avoiding a parametric evaluation of the energy consumption of the cooling units during their operation, accounting instead for the effect of the dynamic variations of load and operating conditions characterizing a standard delivery mission on energy consumption and efficiency of the systems.

The units performance is compared over the same delivery mission, for each month of the year, through the definition of an average mission COP (Eq. (1)) referring to the overall energy characterizing the entire mission rather than on instantaneous power.

$$COP = \frac{E_{evap,TOT}}{E_{comp} + E_{fans}} \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1), $E_{evap,TOT}$ corresponds to the cooling energy delivered in the entirety of the delivery mission and $E_{comp} + E_{fans}$ corresponds to the energy consumption of the cooling unit (compressor and heat exchangers fans). The average mission COP of the R134a unit and of the R744 unit for every month of the year are reported in Table 1, while the relationship between the average mission COP of the two units and the average ambient temperature of the mission day is highlighted in Figure 4.

Table 1 – Comparison between the average mission COP of the R134a and R744 cooling units, for every month of the year.

Month	$T_{amb,avg}$ [°C]	COP_{R134a} [-]	COP_{R744} [-]
Jan	11.6	2.01	1.75
Feb	10.4	2.12	1.83
Mar	12.3	1.95	1.75
Apr	16.6	1.65	1.83
May	21.0	1.43	2.01
Jun	26.4	1.25	1.83
Jul	28.7	1.19	1.73
Aug	29.4	1.17	1.68
Sep	25.4	1.27	1.86
Oct	20.6	1.45	1.98
Nov	15.6	1.71	1.81
Dec	11.5	2.02	1.75

Figure 4 – Average delivery mission COP for the R134a and the R744 cooling units as a function of the average ambient temperature.

The R134a average mission COP decreases almost linearly as the average external temperature increases. On the contrary, the R744 unit mission COP follows the same trend during the hottest months of the year (average external temperatures above 20 °C), with a significantly higher COP compared to the R134a unit COP, while during the coldest months (average external temperatures below 20 °C) the R744 unit COP decreases for decreasing ambient temperature, resulting in a lower mission COP compared to the R134a unit.

The higher nominal cooling power of the R744 unit in fact leads to severe partialization during the colder part of the year. Nevertheless, the R744 unit presents a significant advantage over the R134a unit on the hottest months, when most of the yearly cooling is requested, thus reducing the impact of the coldest months on a yearly basis.

To provide the overall yearly performance of the R134a and the R744 system, a yearly annual mission COP has been evaluated in terms of energy, considering the total cooling energy, the total energy fed to the compressor and to the heat exchangers fans during the whole year. The yearly mission COP of the considered cooling units, as well as the total yearly cooling energy and energy consumption of the units, is then reported in Table 2. The employment of the proposed R744 unit in the considered urban delivery mission, instead of the baseline R134a unit, leads to an increase of the average mission COP equal to +27.5% on a yearly basis.

Table 2 - Comparison between the annual cooling energy production, energy consumption and average mission COP of the R134a and R744 cooling units.

Period	R134a unit			R744 unit		
	$E_{evap,TOT}$ [GJ]	$(E_{comp} + E_{fans})_{TOT}$ [GJ]	COP_{year} [-]	$E_{evap,TOT}$ [GJ]	$(E_{comp} + E_{fans})_{TOT}$ [GJ]	COP_{year} [-]
Year	5.85	4.12	1.42	6.33	3.49	1.81

4.2 Life cycle carbon footprint evaluation

The weight of components, chosen among solutions available in the market, considered for the evaluation of the total weight of the R134a and R744 cooling units is reported in Table 3. The weight of pipelines and minor components such as joint and valves are not considered for the sake of simplicity, as it will add a marginal contribution to the total and it depends on the actual piping and design solution adopted.

A total weight of 68 kg and 156 kg are calculated for the R134a and the R744 units, respectively. Comparing the specific weight per unit of cooling power, it emerges that the increase in mass of the R744 unit is largely due to the increase of the rated cooling power, as the overall specific weight is only 14% higher than the R134a one. This increase can be ascribed to the presence of additional components in the R744 system such as the auxiliary evaporator, the internal heat exchanger and the separator (which are not required in the R134a unit thanks to the presence of the thermostatic valve).

Table 3 – Weight of the components of the R134a and the R744 cooling units.

	Weight [kg]		Specific Weight [kg/kW]	
	R134a unit	R744 unit	R134a unit	R744 unit
Compressor	34	73	11.3	12.2
Condenser / Gas cooler	11	17	3.7	2.8
<i>Evaporator</i>	23	32	7.7	5.3
<i>Auxiliary evaporator</i>	-	27	-	4.5
Evaporator (Total)	23	59	7.7	9.8
Internal heat exchanger	-	2	-	0.3
Separator	-	5	-	0.8
TOTAL	68	156	22.7	26.0

To provide a complete comparison between the R134a and the R744 unit considering the entirety of their life cycle, the total equivalent CO₂ emissions (direct and indirect) of the two units are evaluated.

Three main stages can be identified within the cooling units life cycle: production, accounting for both refrigerant production and cooling unit manufacturing; operation, accounting for the energy consumption of the cooling unit during delivery missions, for the additional fuel consumption needed to transport the unit weight and for the refrigerant leakage in the atmosphere; end of life, accounting for the refrigerant and unit recycling and for the release in the atmosphere of the not recycled part of refrigerant charge. The equivalent CO₂ lifetime emissions of the considered units are presented in Figure 5 according to the above-mentioned subdivision.

Figure 5 – Total lifetime carbon footprint of the R134a cooling unit and the R744 cooling unit.

Most of the total lifetime CO₂ equivalent emissions of the units is related to operation, accounting for 92.4% and 94.5% of the total for the R134a and R744 units, respectively. Despite representing a limited portion of the overall carbon footprint, the production and end of life stages impact is not negligible. The different contributions to the CO₂ equivalent emissions of each of the three considered stages are provided in Figure 6.

Figure 6 – Carbon footprint of the R134a and R744 cooling units life stages: (a) production; (b) operation; (c) end of life.

Considering the production stage (Figure 6a), the production of R134a refrigerant is more energy intensive than the recovery of R744 through CCS processes, and the high GWP of R134a leads to non-negligible emissions due to leakages during the unit assembly. However, the higher number of components and material required to build the R744 unit leads to higher emissions compared to the R134a unit. Overall, the carbon footprint of the production stage is equal to 177.1 kg_{CO2,eq} for the R134a unit and to 183.2 kg_{CO2,eq} for the R744 unit.

Considering the operation stage (Figure 6b), in accordance with the improvement of the annual COP discussed in Section 4.1, the CO₂ equivalent emissions linked to the energy consumption of the R744 unit during its lifetime are 15.2% lower than the ones of the R134a unit. However, the increased weight of the R744 unit leads to a significant penalization in terms of emissions linked to the additional fuel consumption required to carry the unit weight compared to the R134a unit, as they are approximately 2.3 times greater for the R744 unit compared to the R134a unit. It is worth noticing that the emissions linked to the unit energy consumption and the ones linked to the additional fuel consumption due to weight have a comparable influence on the overall results, highlighting that, from a life-cycle sustainability perspective, focusing only on the cycle efficiency might be limiting in the overall system optimization. On the other hand, the R134a and R744 units strongly differ in the emissions linked to leakages, remarking the importance of employing natural refrigerants with negligible GWP. Overall, the carbon footprint of the operation stage is equal to 15577.5 kg_{CO2,eq} for the R134a unit and to 10424.5 kg_{CO2,eq} for the R744 unit.

Finally, considering the end of life stage (Figure 6c), similar considerations compared to the production stage can be done. In fact, the most impacting factors are the emissions linked to the cooling unit recycling, penalizing the R744 unit due to the increased weight, and the ones linked to the release of the non-recovered portion of the refrigerant charge in the atmosphere, penalizing the R134a unit due to the high GWP. Overall, the carbon footprint of the end of life stage is equal to 1104.6 kg_{CO2,eq} for the R134a unit and to 423.4 kg_{CO2,eq} for the R744 unit.

According to the results presented and discussed above, the total carbon footprint of the R134a unit and R744 unit life cycle is summarized in Table 4.

Table 4 – Comparison between the total lifetime carbon footprint of the R134a and the R744 cooling unit.

Type of emissions	Process	Carbon footprint [kg _{CO2,eq}]		Difference [%]
		R134a unit	R744 unit	$\frac{\text{R744 unit} - \text{R134a unit}}{\text{R134a unit}_{\text{TOT}}}$
Indirect emissions	Refrigerant production	37.1	2.4	-0.2%
	Cooling unit manufacturing	78.9	180.7	+0.6%
	Operation	8731.5	7403.4	-7.9%
	Cooling unit additional weight	1315.8	3012.8	+10.1%
	Refrigerant recycling	6.1	-	0.0%
	Cooling unit recycling	182.9	418.8	+1.4%
Direct emissions	Leakages	6506.9	13.0	-38.5%
TOTAL		16859.2	11031.1	-34.6%

As mentioned above, despite the significant COP increase of the R744 unit during operation, the overall indirect emissions of the R744 unit are slightly higher (+6.4%) the R134a unit ones. This result highlights that, from a life cycle sustainability perspective, the reduction of the cooling unit weight through optimized materials choice and components design can lead to significant reductions of a transport refrigeration unit carbon footprint.

It appears clear that the development and availability in the market of components specifically designed for R744 transport refrigeration applications represents a major challenge that needs to be addressed, as the vast majority of components for R744 units currently available are developed for commercial refrigeration applications, characterized by significantly greater dimensions and cooling capacities and generally not strongly influenced by their weight, due to their stationary nature.

Nevertheless, the R744 unit is characterized by almost null direct emissions, while a significant amount (38.6%) of the total carbon footprint of the R134a unit is linked to leakage of the refrigerant in the atmosphere, due to its high GWP.

On the whole, the huge impact of the direct emissions on the R134a unit lifetime carbon footprint leads to a significant improvement of the overall environmental sustainability of the R744 unit (-34.6% of the total lifetime CO₂ equivalent emissions), highlighting the crucial importance of the employment of natural refrigerants for the upcoming future of the refrigerated transport sector.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a baseline R134a cooling unit and a newly developed R744 unit, both designed to provide MT cooling in road transport refrigeration applications, have been compared both in terms of yearly performance during operation in urban multi-drop delivery missions and in terms of overall life cycle carbon footprint, to assess the operational and environmental impact of the employment of natural refrigerants compared to traditionally used HFC refrigerants.

Dynamic numerical simulations highlighted that the R744 unit presents a significantly higher COP during the hottest months of the year, while its performance is degraded during the coldest months, due to the high difference between cooling capacity and cooling demand for low ambient temperatures. However, on a yearly basis, the R744 unit mission COP is 27.5% higher than the R134a one.

The evaluation of the total carbon footprint of the two units over their life cycle highlighted that the R744 unit, compared to the R134a unit, presents lower equivalent emissions linked to operation (-15.2%) thanks to its higher annual unit COP, but higher equivalent emissions linked to the additional fuel consumption to carry the cooling unit weight on the vehicle (+229.0%), due to its increased schematic complexity and components weight. As a result, despite a better annual energy performance of the R744 unit, its indirect emissions are slightly higher (+6.4%) than the ones of the R134a unit.

This outcome underscores that, from a life cycle sustainability perspective, significant reductions in the carbon footprint of transport refrigeration units can be achieved by carefully selecting materials and designing components to reduce the weight of the cooling unit. Additionally, it emphasizes that addressing the challenge of developing and making available components designed specifically for R744 transport refrigeration applications is crucial.

Nevertheless, the high GWP of R134a leads to significant direct emissions due to leakages, resulting in a 34.6% reduction of the total lifetime CO₂ equivalent emissions of the R744 unit, considering both direct and indirect emissions. In addition, it must be pointed out that the employment of natural refrigerant R744 overcomes any potential or unknown negative effect on the ecosystems and human health.

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NOMENCLATURE

<i>COP</i>	coefficient of performance [-]
<i>E</i>	energy [J]
<i>h</i>	specific enthalpy [$\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]
<i>K</i>	global heat transfer coefficient [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$]
<i>p</i>	pressure [kPa]
r_p	pressure ratio [-]
<i>T</i>	temperature [K]

Greek letters

η	efficiency [-]
ω	rotational speed [rev min^{-1}]

Subscripts

amb	ambient
avg	average
comp	compressor
evap	evaporator
i	internal
TOT	total
vol	volumetric

Acronyms

CCS	carbon capture and storage
GHG	greenhouse gases
GWP	global warming potential
HFC	hydrofluorocarbons
HFO	hydrofluoroolefins
HPV	high-pressure valve
IHX	internal heat exchanger
LCV	light commercial vehicle
MT	medium temperature
MTV	mechanical throttling valve
PCM	phase change material
WLTC	worldwide harmonized light vehicles test cycle

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